

ISic3588

Honours for Emperor Volusianus

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2019-07-19 - Jonathan Prag edited the file based on autopsy and study for 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated in 1971, in room 7 of the west portico of the agora

Coordinates

37.997856, 14.262463

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory 30600B

Physical Description

Two joining fragments from a slab of off-white marble with faint blue-grey veining. The upper right corner of the slab is preserved, intact along the upper and right margins, but broken below and to the left. The preserved edges are roughly finished and/or damaged. On the reverse of the stone is a second Latin inscription over two lines (see ISic3589); the left margin of the inscription on the reverse, although regular, does not appear to be original to the inscription, and so the stone appears to have been recut to create the right margin for the text here under discussion; in other words, this text is the second and later of the two preserved.

Dimensions

Height 35.5 cm

Width 38 cm

Depth 2.0-2.7 cm

Layout

Parts of three lines of Latin text are preserved, with guide lines top and bottom of each line.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are V-cut, less neatly executed than the inscription on the other side of the stone (77-78 mm tall, except for final O of line 2, 35 mm). The letters are relatively tall and narrow and become more condensed in lines 2 and 3. All letters have pronounced serifs, acutely angled away from the line on horizontal strokes. N in line 2 leans to the right; F and E have shorter second horizontal; B is open with a smaller upper eye; A on occasion has an extended upper stroke. Word breaks are marked by use of an elegant hedera, often with a long stem.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-3: 77-78 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not measured mm

Text

1. [Imp(eratori) ·] Caes(ari)
 2. [C(aio) · Vibio] Afinio
 3. [Gall]o Bel
 4. [dumniano · Vol]
 5. [usiano ·][---]
- undefined. [---]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy and study for edition of 2017

Translation (en)

To Imperator Caesar Caius Vibius Afinius Gallus Veldumnianus Volusianus...

Commentary

The presence of CAES(ari) and AFINIO provide the key to this text, which appears to be preserved for about 50% of its width, since the first part of the standard titulature of the emperor Volusianus is Imperator Caesar Caius Vibius Afinius (June 251-October 253 AD; see Peachin, M. 1990. Roman Imperial Titulature and Chronology, A.D. 235-284. Amsterdam: J.C. Gieben, at 277-280 for titulature). Given this identification, the most plausible interpretation of the letters BEL (note absence of interpunct after the L, suggesting this is not the end of the word), would seem to be the name Veldumnianus, which follows the name Gallus in most dedications to this emperor. Variant renderings of this presumably unfamiliar (in Sicily) name are fairly common (e.g. AE 1953 no.12 [www.trismegistos.org/text/194304] , Uldum[nia]no, CIL 8 no.22465 [www.trismegistos.org/text/328303] , Voldumiano), but in this case we have an example of the very standard confusion of B and V. The substitution of B for V is more common generally in intervocalic positions, but well attested, particularly in Rome and southern Italy, in the initial position also (see Adams, J. 2007. The Regional Diversification of Latin 200 BC - AD 600. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, at 624-666). Although good statistics for Sicily are not available, the phenomenon is attested on the island.

It is impossible to be certain exactly which of Volusianus' other titles followed in the rest of this text, although the apparent narrowness of the stone implies a shorter rather than a longer text. Most simply one might expect Imperator Caesar Caius Vibius Afinius Gallus Veldumnianus Volusianus Pius Felix Augustus, and at the end perhaps Res Publica Halaesinorum, given that this was the body named in the honorific for the immediately preceding Emperor,

Traianus Decius ISic3587 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3587>]

The earlier inscription ISic3589 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3589>] is on the reverse of this stone.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645667

Bibliography

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. *Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.26

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